

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

Community Cluster

Konservierung und Restaurierung / Conservation Science

Chairs: Kristina Fella (LEIZA); Nathaly Witt (HAWK)

SC Decision: 24.05.2024

Bodies Involved: LEIZA; HAWK; primarily TA 4, with links to the other TAs

External Linking: NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory, Verband der Restauratoren e.V. (VDR)

Subject & Objective

The Community Cluster “Conservation and Restoration/Conservation Science” aims to improve access to and exchange of research data on conservation and restoration processes of various art and cultural artefacts. This CC is addressed to colleagues from all specialist and research areas of conservation and restoration in order to jointly examine the existing overlaps and differences in conservation/restoration-related data and to discuss the importance of the open data concept, the FAIR- and CARE-principles and other open questions. An evaluation of existing domain-specific online data sources, data exchange formats and data management software as well as the existing, published or unpublished terminologies and systems for object and condition description and the conservation and restoration measures and materials used at the individual institutions will serve as a basis. In close cooperation with the CC “Semantic Modelling” semantic links and mapping of existing terminologies as well as community standards for conservation and restoration documentation and procedures as well as historical and prehistoric production techniques in this field will be discussed. On the basis of these discussions, working groups (TWGs) are formed to deal with their subject-specific topics.

Out of Scope

The Community Cluster focuses solely on research data management (RDM) topics in the field of conservation and restoration, such as data exchange, modelling and metadata. It does not include discussions on specific conservation/restoration methods, research results or the development of thesauri and vocabularies. The practical technical implementation or transfer of data (databases) by NFDI4Objects is also not part of the Community Cluster.

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Intended Work Results

The following work results are initially aimed for in the planned TWGs:

- White paper on the environmental analysis of the domainspecific RDM landscape, including cataloguing of existing and established authority files, controlled vocabularies, ontologies, repositories and data models (if available)
- Development and formulation of restoration community standards for documentation models and data exchange formats
- Guidance and recommendations for the transformation of existing, internal, unstructured vocabularies into structured, machine-readable and exchangeable formats and linking with the infrastructures created by NFDI4Objects
- Common minimal metadata definition and ontology for processes in conservation/restoration and technological investigations with regard to historical and prehistoric production techniques